

Extraction-spectrophotometric determination of cadmium in micro quantities with diphenylcarbazone

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A simple and sensitive extractive spectrophotometric method for determination of cadmium is described. In presence of pyridine, cadmium forms a red coloured complex with diphenylcarbazone which is extractable in benzene. The extracted species has an absorption maximum at 533 nm and obeys Beer's law for 0.228–3.65 ppm of Cd, the molar absorptivity being $7.33 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Conditions for colour development and interferences from foreign ions have been studied.

Cadmium is one of the most toxic and environmentally unsafe metal. Its determination in trace quantities is required in environmental studies and in toxicological and geochemical work. Several spectrophotometric methods for determination of cadmium using 2,2'-bipyridine¹, 2-(5-chloro-2-pyridylazo)-5-dimethylaminophenol², 1,10-phenanthroline³ and dithizone³ have been reported.

Dithizone⁴ is universally used as a reagent for spectrophotometric determination of metals. Diphenylcarbazone, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-NH-NH-CO-N=N-C}_6\text{H}_5$, is structurally very similar to dithizone implying that it also possesses considerable potentiality for its use as analytical reagent for determination of metals. Diphenylcarbazone^{5,6} forms coloured complexes with several metals and with cadmium, it forms a 1 : 2 complex⁶.

In the present investigation, it is found that in presence of pyridine, Cd^{II} forms a red coloured complex with diphenylcarbazone which is extractable into benzene. This forms the basis of the present extractive spectrophotometric method for determination of cadmium.

Results and Discussion

The red coloured cadmium-diphenylcarbazone complex system in presence of pyridine is completely extractable into benzene and exhibits λ_{max} at 533 nm against the reagent blank. The Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.228–3.65 ppm of cadmium, the molar absorptivity being $7.33 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The absorbance values of the species are reproducible under similar conditions when the pH of the aqueous phase is around 7.0 ± 0.5 . The optimum pyridine concentration range of the aqueous phase is 2–6%. The presence of pyridine in the system makes the extraction easier. The complex was found to be stable for ~24 h. Among several solvents like 1,2-

dichloroethane, methyl isobutyl ketone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, *n*-butanol, isobutanol and benzene tested for extraction of the complex, benzene was found to be the most suitable. A single extraction with 10 ml of 0.05% solution of diphenylcarbazone in benzene was sufficient to extract 99.9% of Cd^{II} from the aqueous solution containing 2.28–36.5 μg of Cd in 10 ml aqueous solution.

The effect of foreign ions in the determination of cadmium was studied by adding different amounts of foreign ions to 4.5 μg of cadmium. It was found that Cr^{VI} , Fe^{III} and Bi^{III} present in equal amounts and Fe^{II} , Ag^{I} , Pt^{IV} , I^- , SCN^- , Br^- , F^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, citrate, tartarate and thiourea in 10-fold excess of cadmium did not interfere. By using masking agents, interference due to several ions could be checked. In presence of KI solution, 5-fold excess of Pb^{II} and Pd^{II} could be tolerated. Interference due to Hg^{II} could be removed by backwashing the extract with 0.1% KI solution. In presence of Ni^{II} , cadmium could be estimated by prior removal of Ni^{II} by extraction into chloroform with dimethylglyoxime. Tolerance limit of Fe^{III} could be improved by adding NH_4HF_2 as masking agent and that of Cu^{II} by using salicylaldehyde. The method was applied for the determination of cadmium in different synthetic ternary mixtures containing Ni^{II} , Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} , Au^{III} , Fe^{III} and Cr^{VI} . The recovery of cadmium was found to be 97.7–98.9%.

A standard solution containing 0.45 ppm of cadmium was estimated ten times by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.33 with a standard deviation of 0.007 absorbance unit. The present method was found to be simple, rapid and sensitive and provided excellent recovery of cadmium upto 3.65 ppm.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-3210 spectrophotometer with matched

quartz cells (1 cm) and an Elico LI-10 pH meter were used. All chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. grade.

Stock solutions of cadmium was prepared from cadmium sulfate (AnalaR) and estimated⁴ and solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution. A 0.05% solution of diphenylcarbazone was prepared in benzene. A 40% pyridine solution in distilled water was used. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their chlorides, nitrates or sulfates for cationic species and from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts for the anionic species.

Procedure : To an aliquot of cadmium solution (containing 2.28–36.5 µg of Cd), pyridine (40%; 1 ml) was added and its volume made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The pH of the aqueous phase was maintained around 7.0.

To it a 0.05% solution of diphenylcarbazone in benzene (10 ml) was added and the resulting mixture was shaken for 5 min. The organic phase was separated and its absorbance measured at 533 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of cadmium was then calculated from the standard calibration curve.

References

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